

Studies on Some Soluble Palladium(II) Chelates in Aqueous Solution. Part III. Reddish Violet Chelate with Sodium 1-(*o*-Arsonophenylazo)-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate

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A reddish violet 1:1 chelate between palladium(II) and sodium 1-(*o*-arsonophenylazo)-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate has been reported. The chelate ($\lambda_{\max}$ 525 m μ) is stable between pH 1.0 and 12.0. The value of stability constant at pH 3.0 and at 25° is expressed by $\log K=4.4$.

Sodium 1-(*o*-arsonophenylazo)-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate (trivial name, Thoron) is designated by the structure:

It is a suitable ligand for metal ions owing to the presence of donor groups like -O: and an azo group. This compound forms a coloured chelate with thorium(IV)¹, which makes it suited as a colorimetric reagent for this. The present authors have also reported the formation of coloured chelates of this reagent with lanthanum(III)² and uranium(VI)³.

It is well known that the donor properties of the azo group are weak, but azo compounds, which contain a strong donor group in a position *ortho* to the azo group, form very stable chelate rings⁴.

The presence of a hydroxyl group and an arsonic group in *ortho* position to the azo group in this reagent makes it a suitable chelating agent. Both these groups are also

1. Sangal and Dey, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 279.

2. *Idem*, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1963, 322, 107.

3. *Idem*, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1963, 20, 219.

4. Bailar, "Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds", Reinhold, New York, 1956, pp. 74, 754-760

capable of linking the metal ion by removal of a proton. Thus a metal chelate of the reagent may be formed with the following structure:

Since the number of known coloured chelates of palladium (II) is limited, a systematic search for new colorimetric reagents for the platinum metals are in progress in these laboratories and Dey *et al.*^{5,6} have already reported trisodium sulphodichlorohydroxydimethylfuchson dicarboxylate (Chrome Azurol S) and sodium *p*-benzylsulphonate azoresorcin (Tropæolin O) as suitable chromogenic reagents for palladium (II). In the present communication the chelate between palladium (II) and Thoron has been described.

EXPERIMENTAL

Stock solutions of Thoron (B.D. H. reagent) and palladium chloride (Johnson and Matthey) were prepared and standardised. Absorbance and *pH* measurements were made as described earlier⁷.

The composition of the chelate of palladium was studied by three different methods and the stability by the method of Sangal *et al.*⁸.

TABLE I
Total volume=50 ml.

Experiment.	Curve.	$c \times 10^4$.	* <i>p</i> .	$\lambda_{\max}$.	Vol. of PdCl ₂ at peak.	Composition. Pd(II) : Thoron.
I	A	4.00M	1.0	540m μ	25.0ml	1 : 1
	B	2.00	1.0	540	25.0	1 : 1
	C	1.33	1.0	540	25.0	1 : 1
II	A	4.00	1.0	550	25.0	1 : 1
	B	2.00	1.0	550	25.0	1 : 1
	C	1.33	1.0	550	25.0	1 : 1

**p* denotes conc. ratio of the chelating soln.

DISCUSSION

It has been established that only one chelate with $\lambda_{\max}$ at 525 m μ is formed⁹ between the reactants. The chelate is stable between *pH* 1.0 and 12.0. (Fig. 1.). Measurements of absorbance were made at *pH* 3.0. The results obtained by the method of continued variations are summarised in Table I.

5. Sangal and Dey, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 484.

6. Seth and Dey, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 794.

7. Banerji and Dey, *ibid.*, 1961, 38, 139.

8. *Ibid.*, 1963, 40, 275.

9. Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437; 1942, 64, 1830.

The results obtained by the mole-ratio and the slope-ratio methods also confirm the composition of the chelate to be Pd (Thoron), corroborating the findings of Table I.

FIG. 1. Effect of pH on the stability of the chelate.
Final conc. of Thoron = $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. Final conc. of Pd(Cl)₂ = $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

The stability constant at pH 3.0 and 25°, calculated by the method of Sangal *et al.*⁶, is expressed by $\log K = 4.4$ and the corresponding value of $\Delta G^\circ = -6.1$ kcals.

The chelate is neutral as has been noted from adsorption study, using ion-exchange resins.

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